

THE IMPACT OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP STYLE ON CHANGES IN ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION MEDIATED BY PSYCHOLOGICAL EMPOWERMENT IN KENDARI CITY GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

Leadership plays an important role in influencing employee behavior in the organization. The purpose of this research was to examine and analyze the influence of authentic leadership style on psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, and employee job satisfaction, as well as to examine the mediating role of psychological empowerment on these influences. The object of this research was civil servants in 20 departments in Kendari City. The population of this study included all civil servants in the Kendari City Department, where the respondents for this study only included 266 civil servants. The data collection method uses a questionnaire and the analysis tool used is SEM Amos. The results revealed that authentic leadership style had a positive and significant influence on changes in psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. Furthermore, psychological empowerment has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Finally, psychological empowerment was found to partially mediate the influence of authentic leadership style on organizational commitment, and also the influence of authentic leadership style on employee job satisfaction.

Keywords: Authentic Leadership Style, Psychological Empowerment, Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Regional Apparatus Organizations as organizations formed to assist regional government work in serving the community also really need human resources or employees who have good abilities, high commitment, and job satisfaction to be able to work better and optimally in providing services to the community. Organizational commitment is important for every organization to pay attention to, especially government organizations, because commitment that is not properly maintained will result in the ineffectiveness of the organization itself, which will have a negative impact on the organization.

Organizational commitment is one of the focuses of this study, in which an employee supports a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization. Organizational commitment refers to employees' feelings of commitment related to their involvement in the organization (McShane and Von Glinow, 2008). Employees are required to have a high commitment to the organization to achieve organizational goals. Organizational commitment can grow and increase when an organization is run with good leadership, empowering employees to carry out their work. Apart from organizational commitment, satisfaction also makes a significant contribution to the achievement of organizational goals. In public sector organizations, it is very important to pay attention to job satisfaction, and creating job satisfaction will encourage better public services provided by employees. Job satisfaction is the

expectation that employees will fulfill their work. Expectations are an interactive function of needs and values; the greater the needs and the higher the value of these needs, the higher the expectations. Job satisfaction is needed so that employees can perform their duties optimally.

In research conducted by Qing et al. (2020), to support the creation of high organizational commitment and good job satisfaction felt by employees, it is necessary to pay attention to aspects of leadership and empowerment. The leadership aspect is the main aspect of organizational management, where it is the leader who determines the direction of an organization and creates working conditions that can encourage job satisfaction and engagement (Oyewobi, 2022). Leadership involves influencing others to achieve the goals that an organization wishes to achieve. Leadership is the ability to inspire trust and gain support from people who depend on their trust and commitment. All the actions of the leader can influence the commitment and satisfaction felt by individuals in the organization. If the leader is seen as responsible and provides inspiration, then the leader will be able to create engagement among subordinates, resulting in satisfaction at work. The success of service-oriented organizations depends on the role of their leaders because leaders can influence the emotions, attitudes, and behavior of individuals in the organization. Leaders can also change subordinates to prioritize organizational interests over personal interests and change their morals, ideals, interests, and values, encouraging them to do better than expected (Pieterse et al., 2010).

Previous research on the influence of leadership style on commitment and job satisfaction has found mixed results. Research by Qing et al. (2020) in government organizations found that leadership style was able to properly influence the commitment of members of the organization, and this leadership style was also able to create job satisfaction. Furthermore, Oyewobi (2022) stated that a good leadership style applied to a work unit will lead to good commitment and job satisfaction felt by members of the organization. Findings from Joo and Nam (2019) reveal that leadership makes a good contributes to creating the job satisfaction felt by organizational members. Yousaf and UI Hadi (2020) revealed that authentic leadership can encourage good work commitment. However, on the other hand, Huang, Liu, Huang (2020) revealed that differences in leadership styles can have an insignificant influence on creating commitment when existing leaders are not able to implement it well.

According to Robbins and Judge (2015), theories that increase understanding of effective leadership do not explicitly explain the role of ethics and trust, with some researchers arguing that these two components are important to complete the picture of leadership. Leadership concepts that include these two components include authentic leadership (Avolio and Gardner 2005). Authentic leaders know who they are, what values they believe in, and act openly and openly in accordance with these values and beliefs (Robbins and Judge, 2015). In authentic leadership, followers consider their leaders to be ethical (Robbins and Judge, 2015). According to Yousaf and UI Hadi (2020), authentic leadership has inspired employees to put in more effort, increase organizational commitment, and create better psychological conditions for employees. The main quality that authentic leadership produces is trust because authentic leaders disseminate information and encourage open communication.

Furthermore, the effective implementation of an authentic leadership style in the organization will lead to better psychological conditions for subordinates. The concept of psychological empowerment proposed by Conger and Kanungo (1988) states that increasing individual motivation in the workplace is through the delegation of authority by leaders to the lowest levels in an organization, so that competent decisions can be made. A good leadership style that is applied to support psychological empowerment by dividing or transferring power to people who perform the work concerned will be able to support the psychological perceptions of organizational members.

Psychological empowerment refers to the internal process of individuals within an organization that is empowered or has authority to carry out their duties. Individuals who feel empowered because of mutual support from leaders and the organization will be able to optimize their abilities, which will ultimately create a sense of attachment to the organization, as well as job satisfaction. Empowerment in an organizational context is an action taken to share power and decision making; empowered employees will feel better about their work and themselves and can then increase their job satisfaction (Hechanova et al., 2006). Employees' psychological empowerment is a form of freedom in which they make decisions to ensure maximum satisfaction. Psychological empowerment is a fundamental starting point and an extraordinary aspect of achieving organizational success. Empowerment provides employees with the opportunity to use their abilities to perform work under smooth conditions, which can increase organizational commitment. Empowerment will increase employees' commitment because empowerment helps increase participation more effectively and ensures that everything can be done well.

In previous research related to the goodness of psychological empowerment in creating commitment and job satisfaction, Qing et al. (2020) revealed that the psychological empowerment felt by individuals in organizations can encourage them to do the things they want. This is related to the individual's confidence in their abilities and skills in carrying out their duties. Perceived good psychological empowerment will lead to the creation of positive work commitment and perceived job satisfaction due to their positive perception of their work abilities. Al-Hussein (2020) concludes that psychological empowerment has a significant influence on organizational commitment. Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020) also stated that psychological empowerment plays a positive role in creating work commitment. On the other hand, Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020) stated that not only will commitment be created from a good perception of psychological empowerment but will also provide satisfaction at work when this can be fulfilled.

LITERATUR REVIEW

Leadership

A leader is essentially someone who has the ability to influence the behavior of other people in their work by using their power. Power is the ability to direct and influence other people regarding the tasks that must be carried out. According to Stone (2004), the greater the number of sources of power available to a leader, the greater is the potential for effective leadership. Davis and Newstrom (2001) define leadership as the process of encouraging and helping others to work enthusiastically to achieve goals. Gibson et al, (1995) also stated that leadership is an effort to use a type of influence rather than coercion to motivate people to achieve certain goals. Successful

leadership is a behavior that unites and provides stimuli for followers to achieve goals set in certain situations. Based on this statement, leadership is the use of influence, not coercion, to motivate organizational members and encourage and help others work to achieve goals.

According to Rivai and Mulyadi (2012:2) includes the process of influencing the determination of organizational goals, motivating follower behavior to achieve goals, and influencing the improvement of the group and its culture. In addition, it also influences the interpretation of events by followers, organizing and activities to achieve goals, maintaining cooperative relationships and group work, and obtaining cooperative support from people outside the group or organization.

Authentic Leadership Style

An authentic leadership style is a process that combines a positive leadership position and commitment given in the context of building an organization. Studies on this topic mostly link authentic leadership domains to psychological approaches (Northouse, 2013:263). Authentic leaders change when they raise awareness about what is true, good, important, and beautiful when they help alleviate followers' needs for achievement, self-actualization, and moral authority, and when they challenge followers to move beyond their self-interest for the good of the group, the organization, or society. George (2003:18) explains that authentic leadership is a type of leadership that prioritizes self-awareness above other dimensions, which in practice must pay attention to the five dimensions of authentic leadership, namely understanding goals, practicing with solid values, being full of heart, establishing strong relationships, well and shows self-discipline. Based on this, authentic leadership prioritizes changes that come from within a leader. A leader who has authentic leadership within himself means that he understands his goals at work, applies solid values, works wholeheartedly, builds good relationships with his employees, and fosters a sense of self-discipline within himself.

According to Walumbwa et al. (2008), authentic leadership is leadership with behavior that encourages and shows positive and principled behavior that fosters self-awareness, an internalized moral perspective, balances information before decision-making, and has the character of relational transparency. According to Bateman and Snell (2008), authentic leadership is a leadership style in which the leader acts honestly towards himself when leading. Shamir and Eilam (2005:399) define authentic leadership as people who have the attributes, First, the role of leader is the main component of the self-concept of authentic leadership, Second, they have reached a high level of self-resolution or self-concept. Third, their goal is in accordance with their own desires. Fourth, their behavior was expressive. Leaders with an honest leadership style will have awareness and self-confidence towards growing openness regarding their followers (Begley, 2006)

Psychological Empowerment

The concept of psychological empowerment has been introduced by several researchers, including Conger and Kanungo (1988), who defined psychological empowerment as a motivational concept of self-fulfillment, which can be more specific for workers. Spreitzer (1995) states that psychological empowerment is a condition that involves employee cognition as a form of support that is expected to increase an individual's ability to produce proactive behavior in the organizational environment.

The psychological empowerment perspective refers to the internal process of individuals feeling empowered (Menon, 2001) because psychological empowerment exists or emerges when workers feel that they exercise control over their work lives (Spreitzer, 1995). Thomas and Velthouse (1990) argue that positive outcomes produced by workers are determined by the worker's personal perception of empowerment, which personal perception is psychological empowerment, and is not completely determined by structural empowerment by the organization. Therefore, psychological empowerment is an important concept in research because it is related to the concept of empowerment, which originates within the individual.

Zimmerman (1995) suggested that psychological empowerment is a process involving individuals, organizations, and communities that aims to jointly create a better environment than before. This process involves the development of personal skills and competencies. In line with this, psychological empowerment reflects individuals who are able to reflect on themselves as competent individuals or are able to feel empowered in their work environment. Thus, individuals can demonstrate more positive performance and encourage more active contributions to an organization.

Organizational Commitment

The concept of commitment as a form of individual work attitude in organizations has become an important emphasis in the human relations school of thought, especially in Elton Mayo (Forness and Rocco, 2004). Even Becker (1992), Blau (1987), Wiener and Vardi (1980) in Cohen (1999) stated that commitment is an important predictor such as employee turnover intentions, performance, job satisfaction, prosocial behavior, absenteeism levels, and employee inertia at work.

According to Meyer et al. (1993) and Forness and Rocco (2004), commitment can be defined as the level of assurance or binding of an individual to a set of behaviors and motivates someone to act. Thus, commitment is dedication or a sense of emotional attachment that manifests through a person's motivation and behavior to do something. The term "something" in this context can refer to an organization, work unit, work team, or task/job.

The concept of organizational commitment is based on the premise that individuals can form attachments with the organizations in which they work. This attachment is characterized by an intention to remain with the organization (identifying with its values and goals) and a willingness to exert extra effort on its behalf (Porter et al., 1974). Therefore, organizational commitment goes beyond passive loyalty and requires an active relationship with the organization, so that individuals are willing to give something of themselves to contribute to the well-being of the organization (Mowday et al., 1974)

Job Satisfactor

Each individual has a different level of job satisfaction, according to the value system that applies to them. The higher the perception of job satisfaction in accordance with an individual's wishes, the higher the job satisfaction with the activity. Renyut et al (2017) revealed that successful organizations are always characterized by job satisfaction. Expectancy theory states that a person's job satisfaction is assessed based on the fulfillment of goals, achievements, realizations, targets, and well-being. The more expectations that are met, the more satisfied the work will be. It cannot be denied that job satisfaction is currently an important thing to remember when carrying

out work activities; every employee is faced with job competition, so they are required to continue to increase job satisfaction.

According to Robbins and Judge (2015, p.78), job satisfaction is a general attitude towards a person's work that shows the difference between the amount of appreciation workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive. Job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects of a person's work, and job satisfaction is not a single concept. A person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of their job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects (Hasibuan, 2005:202).

Job satisfaction is the (positive) attitude of workers towards their work, which arises based on an assessment of the work situation. This assessment can be carried out on one's work, and it is carried out as a sense of appreciation for achieving one of the important values in the work. Satisfied employees liked their work situation more than disliked it. Feelings related to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction tend to reflect employees' assessments of current and past work experiences rather than their expectations for the future. Thus, it can be concluded that there are two important elements in job satisfaction: work values and basic needs (Robbins & Judge, 2015:46).

Research Hypothesis

Authentic leadership style on Psychological Empowerment

Authentic leadership, which involves delegating responsibilities to subordinates, can increase their ability to believe in generating creative and unique ideas. Authentic leadership can encourage psychological empowerment when authentic leadership is implemented. Research findings from Yousaf and Ul Hadi (2020) state that authentic leadership plays an important role in increasing employee psychological empowerment efforts. Leadership that is carried out well and always has a positive connotation will encourage the creation of good psychological conditions that will result in an increase in employee empowerment. Another finding from Sandhu, Dastgeer, & Haq (2019) also stated the same thing that one of the factors that can create psychological empowerment is a good authentic leadership style applied in an organization. In research conducted by Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020), it was also stated that the changes that occur in organizations are caused by how leadership is carried out, and good leadership will be able to create conditions where employees will be psychologically empowered. Based on this explanation, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H1: Authentic leadership style has a positive and significant effect on psychological empowerment

Authentic Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment

Authentic leadership has a significant influence on organizational commitment. Effective leaders influence their followers to have greater optimism, self-confidence, and commitment to the organization's goals and mission. This is reinforced by previous research findings from Yousaf and Ul Hadi (2020), who stated that there is a significant influence between authentic leadership styles and organizational commitment possessed by members of the organization. Oyewobi (2022) findings also strengthen this, concluding that authentic leadership style is an important factor in creating high organizational commitment for every employee. Another finding from Surucu (2022) is that improvements in authentic leadership styles in organizations can form higher commitment when leaders are able to implement values that are in line

with employee expectations. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H2: Authentic leadership style has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment

Authentic Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

Authentic leadership that is carried out well can create job satisfaction when leaders with an authentic style are able to create a positive environment that is in line with work flow. Research findings conducted by Sakic et al,(2019) state that the authentic leadership style applied in an organization has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction. Likewise, findings from Oyewobi (2022) also concluded that authentic leadership style has a high contribution to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be achieved when leaders meet the expectations of existing employees. Venegas et al. (2022) in their research also concluded that employees can experience higher job satisfaction when the authentic leadership style applied by superiors meets their expectations. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H3: Authentic leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Psychological Empowerment on Organizational Commitment

Psychological empowerment implemented well by the organization will make existing employees feel comfortable at work, and this will increase their commitment to the organization. This statement is supported by previous research findings from Qing et al. (2020), who found that psychological empowerment can significantly and positively influence employees' affective commitment. Yousaf and Ul Hadi (2020) also revealed that the psychological empowerment given to employees can encourage them to work well because they are given the freedom to work and this will ultimately increase their commitment to their workplace. Other findings from Sandhu, Dastgeer, & Haq (2019) also state that psychological empowerment has a significant impact on creating aspects of organizational commitment. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H4: Psychological empowerment has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment

Psychological Empowerment on Job Satisfaction

Qing et al. (2020) in their research concluded that the psychological empowerment provided by organizations can significantly increase employees' job satisfaction. Findings from AlKahtani et al. (2021) also reveal the same thing that good empowerment provided by work units can create job satisfaction. Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020) in their research also state that psychological empowerment has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction. Alagarsamy et al. (2020) revealed that psychological empowerment has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H5: Psychological empowerment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Authentic Leadership Style on Organizational Commitment Through Psychological Empowerment

An organization with a good level of psychological empowerment can support the leadership's direction in creating employee commitment to the organization. Authentic leadership gives subordinates the freedom to adapt to their work. Previous research findings from Yousaf and UI Hadi (2020) explain that psychological empowerment can positively support the implementation of an authentic leadership style to create better organizational commitment. Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020) in their research also revealed that psychological empowerment partially mediates the influence of authentic leadership styles on organizational commitment.

Other findings from Sandhu, Dastgeer, & Haq (2019) also concluded that psychological empowerment was able to mediate the influence of authentic leadership on organizational commitment. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H6: Psychological empowerment mediates the influence of authentic leadership style on organizational commitment

Authentic Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction Through Psychological Empowerment

Job satisfaction is an important aspect that must be addressed. One factor that can create job satisfaction is the good leadership style applied by superiors in an organization and the psychological empowerment given to employees. Research findings from Qing et al. (2020) reveal that the leadership style applied by an organization can create job satisfaction when it meets expectations, and will be even more optimal when leaders are able to provide empowerment, especially psychological empowerment, to their employees.

Research findings from Bharadwaja and Tripathi (2020) also revealed that psychological empowerment partially mediates the effect of authentic leadership on job satisfaction. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated in this research:

H7: Psychological empowerment mediates the effect of authentic leadership style on job satisfaction

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework

Research Method

This research design uses a positivist paradigm with an explanatory research type in which data collection is carried out using cross-sections. This research was included in the survey research category because the data collection used an instrument in the form of a questionnaire. The unit of analysis studied in this research was employees of the Department of Kendari City. This research took all employees at the Department in Kendari City as the population and then used cluster proportional sampling to divide the population into several groups so that the respondents in this study were 266 employees. Sampling was performed using a simple random sampling technique. The research data were collected by distributing questionnaires to all employees who met the research sample criteria. The collected data were analyzed using SEM-AMOS.

This study used three types of variables: independent, mediating, and dependent. The independent variable, namely authentic leadership style, in this study was measured by four indicators from Walumbwa et al. (2008):

- (1) self-awareness,
- (2) balance processing,
- (3) relational transparency, and
- (4) internalized moral perspective.

The mediating variable, psychological empowerment, is measured by indicators from Spreitzer et al. (1997), which consists of

- (1) meaning,
- (2) competence,
- (3) self-determination, and
- (4) impact.

Finally, the dependent variable is organizational commitment, which is measured by indicators from Allen and Meyer (1990) and consists of

- (1) affective commitment,
- (2) continuous commitment, and
- (3) normative commitment,

As well as the job satisfaction variable, which is measured by indicators from Warr, Cook, and Wall (1979) in Stride et al. (2007) and consists of

- (1) intrinsic satisfaction and
- (2) extrinsic satisfaction.

RESULTS

Of the total questionnaires distributed, 287 were returned, and 266 respondents met the criteria. Based on this, a descriptive analysis of the characteristics of existing respondents shows that the majority were aged 40 – 47 years (42%), with the majority being men (63%) compared to women (37%). Looking at the educational level of employees, the majority had a bachelor's degree (53%) with most years of service in the range of 9 to 16 years (58%). This shows that the respondents were able to

understand every aspect that will be studied well, both in terms of existing leadership styles, understanding of perceived empowerment, and attitudes of commitment and satisfaction with the work undertaken.

Convergent Validity

First, the loading factor should be significant. The loading factors to determine convergent validity can be seen in the standardized regression weight (loading estimate) table. The results of the standardized regression weights are shown in Table 2. Based on Table 2 presented, it can be seen that the standardized loading estimate output results are all above 0.50, so it can be concluded that the indicators for each construct are able to reflect the latent variables. Therefore, the existing indicators can be said to be convergently valid.

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Respondents

Category	Quantity (People)	Percentage (%)
Age 24 - 31 years	50	19
Age 32 - 39 years	65	24
Age 40 - 47 years	111	42
Age 48 - 56 years	40	15
Male	167	63
Female	99	37
Senior high school	6	2
Associate's degree	43	16
Bachelor degree	142	53
Master degree	54	20
Doctoral degree	21	8
Exp 1 - 8 years	34	13
Exp 9 - 16 years	153	58
Exp 17 - 24 years	68	26
Exp ≥ 25 years	11	4

Table 2: Standardized Regression Weight (Factor Loading)

			Estimate
X1	<---	Autentik_Leadership	.930
X2	<---	Autentik_Leadership	.844
X3	<---	Autentik_Leadership	.916
X4	<---	Autentik_Leadership	.884
Y1.1	<---	Psychological_Empowerment	.878
Y1.2	<---	Psychological_Empowerment	.870
Y1.3	<---	Psychological_Empowerment	.887
Y1.4	<---	Psychological_Empowerment	.864
Y2.1	<---	Organizational_Commitment	.887
Y2.2	<---	Organizational_Commitment	.849
Y2.3	<---	Organizational_Commitment	.941
Y3.1	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.890
Y3.2	<---	Job_Satisfaction	.892

Reliability

High construct reliability indicates internal consistency, meaning that all measurements consistently represent the construct. Construct reliability can be interpreted as the extent to which a measurement instrument is reliable or trustworthy. Table 3 shows the results of the contract reliability test.

Table 3: Construct Reliability

Item Indicator	Loading Factor	Construct Reliability
X1	0.930	0.94091
X2	0.844	
X3	0.916	
X4	0.884	
Y1.1	0.878	0.92877
Y1.2	0.870	
Y1.3	0.887	
Y1.4	0.864	
Y2.1	0.887	0.92192
Y2.2	0.849	
Y2.3	0.941	
Y3.1	0.890	0.88510
Y3.2	0.892	

From Table 3, it can be seen that the overall construct reliability value is greater than the cutoff value of 0.6. Therefore, the variables in this study are considered reliable for measuring the construct.

Goodness Of Fit

The purpose of this test is to determine whether the model fits existing sample data. The goodness of fit test results are shown in the table below.

Table 4: Goodness Of Fit Overall Model Fit

Goodness Of Fit Index	Cut off Value	Result	Information
Chi-Square	Expected to be smaller	119.490	χ^2 with df = 60, sig 5% (79.082)-Marginal
Significancy Probablity	$\geq 0,05$	0.000	Marginal
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,0$	1.991	Good
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.933	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0.061	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.899	Marginal
TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0.961	Good
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.971	Good
PNFI	0,60 – 0,90	0.747	Good
PGFI	0 – 1,0	0.615	Good

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the goodness-of-fit evaluation results are good results, there are 7 out of 10 criteria that meet the cut-off value. Even though some indexes are still below the cut-off value or are classified as marginal, these values are not too far from the cut-off value. In this case, a marginal value indicates that the value is closest to the standard and is still considered feasible. Hair (2010) also believes that researchers do not need to report or show all goodness-of-fit indices, although they sometimes do not adequately represent the model suitability test. Therefore, by reporting several values that meet the cutoff value, sufficient information can be provided to evaluate the model. Thus, it can be concluded that the model fits the existing data, and the model is acceptable.

Figure 2: Full Structural Equation Model

Hypothesis Testing

The causality test aims to determine the causal relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables. In addition, we test the hypothesis formulation. The results of the regression weight tests are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Regression Weight Parameter Estimates

Hypothesis				Estimate	C.R.	P	Results
H1	Authentic Leadership	→	Psychological Empowerment	0.946	18.761	0.000	Support
H2	Authentic Leadership	→	Organizational Commitment	0.281	2.316	0.021	Support
H3	Authentic Leadership	→	Job Satisfaction	0.444	3.766	0.000	Support
H4	Psychological Empowerment	→	Organizational Commitment	0.715	5.724	0.000	Support
H5	Psychological Empowerment	→	Job Satisfaction	0.533	4.499	0.000	Support

Based on the output of the Regression Weight parameter estimates in Table 5, it can be concluded that H1 which tests authentic leadership style on employee psychological empowerment has an estimated path coefficient value of 0.946 with a p-value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$ and a C.R value of $18,761 > 1.96$ which is interpreted as as having a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that authentic leadership styles have a positive and significant influence on psychological empowerment. Furthermore, in testing H2, the estimated path coefficient value was 0.281 with a p-value of $0.021 < \alpha = 0.05$, and a C.R value of $2.316 > 1.96$; thus, it can be concluded that authentic leadership style has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment. H3 looks at the influence of authentic leadership style on employee job satisfaction and obtained an estimated value of 0.444 with a p-value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, and a C.R value of $3,766 > 1.96$, which is interpreted as a

significant influence. Based on these results, it can be concluded that H1, H2, and H3 tested in this study are acceptable.

Furthermore, in testing psychological empowerment on organizational commitment and job satisfaction it was found that, H4 psychological empowerment on organizational commitment obtained an estimated path coefficient value of 0.715 with a p-value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$ and a C.R value of $5.724 > 1.96$ which is interpreted as there is a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that psychological empowerment has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment, and that in H5, the estimated path coefficient value is 0.533 with a p-value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, and a C.R value of $4.499 > 1.96$, which is interpreted as having a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that psychological empowerment has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction, meaning that the better the psychological empowerment felt by employees, the higher their job satisfaction they feel will be. Thus, H4 and H5 proposed in this study can be accepted.

Next, a mediation effect test was conducted to determine the nature of the relationship between the variables. The approach to testing the mediating variables in this research can be carried out using z-statistics developed by Sobel. The Sobel Test results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Mediation Testing

Mediation Effect	p-value	Results
Authentic Leadership → Psychological Empowerment → Organizational Commitment	0.000	Significant mediate
Authentic Leadership → Psychological Empowerment → Job Satisfaction	0.000	Significant mediate

Based on Table 6, H6, which tested the mediating role of psychological empowerment, found that psychological empowerment mediated the influence of authentic leadership style on organizational commitment, as evidenced by a significance value of 0.000 (< 0.05). Thus, Hypothesis 6 in this study is accepted. The estimated values were compared to determine the nature of the mediation hypothesis. The results found that The estimated value of indirect influence was greater than the estimated value of direct influence, where each influence was significant. Therefore, it can be concluded that psychological empowerment plays the role of partial mediation. Furthermore, in testing H7, psychological empowerment was found to mediate the influence of authentic leadership style on job satisfaction, as evidenced by a significance value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on this, it can be concluded that psychological empowerment can mediate the influence of authentic leadership styles on job satisfaction. Thus, Hypothesis 7 in this study is accepted. Looking at the existing influence, it can be seen that the H7 mediation eel is partial.

DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis show that the authentic leadership style can create positive, empowering, and inspiring working conditions, which makes employees feel comfortable and encouraged to work better because of the freedom given to carry out their duties according to their abilities. knowledge possessed. An authentic leadership style can provide positive aspects for employees, where it directs leaders to always be open and accept any changes that occur.

An authentic leadership style can create a good relationship between leaders and subordinates, where this leadership style supports transparency and good moral attitudes towards work and subordinates, which will make existing employees feel more comfortable working like their leaders. In general, employees who receive attention or have conditions where they can be closer to their leaders, both in conveying ideas or suggestions and in the process of solving the problems they face, are more interested in remaining in their work unit and will not want to move to another work unit or agency in the future. This means that they have a high commitment to their organizations. Therefore, it is important for City Services to optimize this leadership style to improve the relationship between employees and organizations.

Authentic leadership also plays an important role in creating job satisfaction in employees. Job satisfaction can be obtained from external aspects which include working conditions that have been regulated by the leadership, good management carried out by the leadership, harmonious working conditions between co-workers and good communication with superiors as well as positive views of the leadership towards their subordinates will lead to achieving satisfaction. higher work. Therefore, it is important for Kendari City Department to optimize the application of an authentic leadership style to continue to support and create job satisfaction for employees.

Based on the results of the analysis of the role of psychological empowerment on organizational commitment and job satisfaction, it was found that psychological empowerment has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This can be interpreted to mean that the better the psychological empowerment efforts provided by the Department in Kendari City for employees in carrying out their work, the better the impact on their commitment to their work unit and organization. Empowerment relates to control over one's work life. Organizations that provide freedom for employees to manage their work roles in a more meaningful way will lead to higher levels of commitment. On the other hand, one of the aims of providing psychological empowerment is to give them freedom to work and understand their abilities to carry out their work. Optimizing this will make employees happy with their work and ultimately create job satisfaction, both internally and externally. Therefore, it is important for the Kendari City Department to pay attention to the psychological empowerment of employees so that they can experience high job satisfaction and produce satisfactory organizational work performance.

CONCLUSION

This research can conclude several things, including that authentic leadership style has an important role in increasing perceived psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction from activities within the organization. Through this, the Kendari City Department needs to pay attention to the implementation of an authentic leadership style, especially with respect to the openness of relationships held by service leaders, where optimizing the openness of the relationships aspect of the leadership applied will support increasing employee empowerment, commitment, and job satisfaction.

Psychological empowerment is an important aspect that organizations must pay attention to. The psychological empowerment provided by the organization can form a deep attachment to employees because they feel that they have the freedom to use all their abilities to complete their work according to their own methods. Freedom was

also found to create high levels of satisfaction, indicating the importance of empowerment in an organization. In addition, the findings of this research also reveal that psychological empowerment can be a bridge in optimizing authentic leadership implemented by an organization to create commitment and job satisfaction felt by employees.

Several aspects need to be improved for each existing variable, including increasing employee job satisfaction. Organizations can focus on fulfilling employee needs regarding rewards, appropriate responsibilities, equal opportunities between employees, and the variety of tasks given. In addition, in terms of organizational commitment, organizations need to pay attention to the normative aspects of the commitment created and make improvements, especially in employees' sense of responsibility for their work and employee loyalty, where existing employees need to be given treatment that can increase their loyalty and have greater opportunities for promotion. Finally, in the aspect of psychological empowerment, organizations need to increase the meaningfulness of employees' tasks and the competence of employees so that they can be more empowered in carrying out their work.

LIMITATION

The research was not free from limitations. There are several limitations to this research, which are one way for future research to develop. First, this research was conducted based on a survey that has limitations in presenting cross-sectional relationship analysis; therefore, the changes that occur thereafter cannot be controlled. Therefore, to identify existing changes, further research is needed to determine whether the relationships between the variables analyzed in this research have changed. Second, this research could not explore the application of authentic leadership style, psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction through in-depth interviews with respondents; thus, information about the research variables was only obtained based on the research questionnaire. Finally, this research was limited to Kendari City Government Implementing Agencies, where conditions will be different from those of other Government Agencies. Thus, this can limit the ability to generalize the research findings, especially to other governments or privately owned agencies or organizations. For this reason, it is hoped that further research can be conducted on a wider scope so that the findings of this research can be generalized. Further research can test other leadership styles, such as situational leadership, to examine the role of leadership in dynamic conditions.

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